

Spectrophotometric Studies of the Chelate of Cu(II) with Schiff's Base (AHN) 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthal Aniline

Y. N. BHATT, K. K. PATEL, K. J. SHAH & R. S. PATEL*

University Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar

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USUALLY complexes of Schiff's bases are studied in solid state. Literature reveals that study of such complexes in solution is limited. Therefore, the spectrophotometric study of the composition and stability of the chelate formed in solution by Schiff's base (AHN) with Cu(II) has been undertaken in this laboratory.

Experimental and Results

2-Hydroxy-1-naphthal aniline was prepared by refluxing aniline with 2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde for 45 min at 60° in ethyl alcohol. It was also recrystallised in ethyl alcohol. M.P. of the compound was 92°. The compound was first prepared by Savich¹ and his coworkers.

The solution of the ligand was prepared in analar grade dioxane. The stock solution of copper nitrate was prepared by dissolving calculated amount of A.R. grade copper nitrate in double distilled water. It was estimated by standard gravimetric and volumetric methods.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made on Bausch and Lomb "Spectronic-20" spectrophotometer at 30° ± 1° in 50% dioxane water, v/v medium.

The method of Vosburgh and Copper² was employed to determine the nature of the complex. Mixtures containing 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 molar ratio of Cu(II) to ligand were prepared. Absorption spectra gave two peaks, one at 405 nm where ligand absorption was appreciable and other at 495 nm where ligand absorbance was negligible. So all measurements were carried out at this wave length of 495 nm. Effect of variation of pH on the degree of complex formation was studied at 495 nm. The pH of the solutions was adjusted by using Michaelis buffer solutions. The optimum pH range was observed to be 8-10 in which the complex was found to be stable for several days.

The composition of the complex was determined by three different methods; Job's³ using equimolar solutions, Slope ratio⁴ and molar ratio⁵. It was found to be 1 : 1 in all cases.

The average apparent stability constant $\log K = 4.08$ of the complex was calculated from absorbance data obtained by molar ratio and Dey and Banerjee⁶ methods.

The free energy of its formation at 30°C was found to be 5700 calories/mole.

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Pyrimidines : Part IX : Synthesis of Some Bis(arylamino)pyrimidines

D. SEN & P. K. DUTTA

Department of Applied Chemistry,
University Colleges of Science and Technology,
Calcutta University, Calcutta-9

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IT has been shown that some pyrimidines having a (substituted)-amino group at C-2 or C-4 and an amino or a (substituted)-amino group at C-4 or C-2 positions exhibit significant antimalarial activity^{1,2}. Some other compounds of these types are also known to exhibit antibacterial and antifolic activity³. It therefore appears likely that 2,4-bis(arylamino)-pyrimidines (I) and isomeric compounds (II) will exhibit interesting biological properties.

In the present paper synthesis of some compounds of types I and II is being reported.

The compounds were synthesised by refluxing 2,4-dichloro-6-amino pyrimidine⁴ or 2-amino-4,6-dichloropyrimidine⁵ with two equivalents of the appropriate amine in glacial acetic acid in presence of small amounts of hydrochloric acid⁶. These are white crystalline solids, insoluble in water but soluble in alcohol.

The spectral data and other details about the compounds are given in Table 1.

* Senior author.